

The Influence of Transformational Leadership and Perceived Organizational Support on Innovative Work Behaviour Mediated by Work Engagement among Civil Servants at PPSDM Regional Yogyakarta

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ABSTRACT: The low level of innovative work behaviour at PPSDM Regional Yogyakarta is reflected in the institution’s 2024 accreditation result, which was rated at the one-star category, as well as the limited contribution of new ideas from employees. This condition highlights the importance of understanding internal organizational factors that can foster IWB, particularly the roles of transformational leadership, organizational support, and work engagement. This study aims to analyze the effects of transformational leadership and perceived organizational support on innovative work behaviour and to examine the mediating role of work engagement among civil servants at PPSDM Regional Yogyakarta. A quantitative approach was employed using a survey method, involving 108 civil servants. Data were analyzed using Partial Least Square–Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM). The findings indicate that transformational leadership and perceived organizational support directly influence IWB. Both variables also have a positive and significant effect on work engagement. Furthermore, work engagement was found to have a positive and significant impact on IWB. Work engagement also significantly mediates the effects of transformational leadership and perceived organizational support on IWB. These results emphasize that work engagement serves as a key mechanism linking leadership and organizational support to employees’ innovative behaviour. Enhancing employees’ IWB cannot be achieved solely through transformational leadership or organizational support; instead, strengthening work engagement as a central mediator is essential. Organizations need to foster employee involvement by improving support, appreciation, and the consistency of policies to build a sustainable innovation culture in the workplace.

KEYWORDS: Innovative Work Behaviour, Perceived Organizational Support, Transformational Leadership, Work Engagement.

INTRODUCTION

Innovative work behaviour (IWB) has become a critical component in enhancing the performance of public organizations in the era of modern bureaucracy. IWB reflects employees’ ability to generate new ideas, develop creative solutions, and implement valuable innovations in public services—an essential demand of bureaucratic reform and improved governance quality. IWB is shaped by motivational factors, individual cognition, and environmental support, all of which influence employees’ capacity to produce and apply innovation. Shifts in the strategic environment, increasing demands for public service quality, and the need for organizational efficiency further encourage public-sector institutions to strengthen the innovative capacity of civil servants as part of ongoing adaptation to policy dynamics and societal needs.[1]

The importance of innovation among civil servants has grown alongside increasingly stringent accreditation requirements for government training institutions. The National Institute of Public Administration (LAN) has developed an accreditation system to assess service quality, resource governance, and organizational innovation capacity. Results of the 2024 accreditation process show that all regional units under BPSDM Kemendagri, including PPSDM Regional Yogyakarta, were placed in the one-star category, indicating a pressing need to improve institutional quality and foster an innovative employee culture. This situation suggests that government organizations continue to face challenges in creating a work ecosystem conducive to innovation, particularly in ensuring that innovation processes move beyond conceptualization and evolve into sustainable solutions.

PPSDM Regional Yogyakarta holds a strategic position within the national competency development system, serving training participants from various regions—including Java, NTB, NTT, and Bali—with more than 2,000 civil servants trained annually, the highest among all regional centers. Ideally, this wide service coverage should be aligned with strong internal capacity for organizational innovation. However, empirical observations indicate that the innovation culture within PPSDM remains suboptimal.

A preliminary survey conducted by the researchers revealed low levels of IWB among employees, reflected in limited innovation creation, minimal idea generation, weak idea implementation, and low engagement in observing or adapting innovations from other units.

The low level of IWB is further reinforced by the accreditation score of 83.58, placing PPSDM Regional Yogyakarta within the one-star category. Accreditation recommendations emphasized the need to strengthen internal innovation culture as one of the institution's weakest areas. Several factors are suspected to contribute to this condition, including limited managerial support, insufficient resources for piloting innovative ideas, and weak monitoring and evaluation systems related to innovation implementation. These issues indicate a gap between organizational expectations for innovative employee behaviour and employees' actual capacity to deliver such behaviour.

IWB can be influenced by various factors, including leadership style, organizational support, and employees' psychological states. Transformational leadership is considered a leadership style capable of stimulating innovation through inspiration, intellectual stimulation, and individualized support. Transformational leaders act as change agents who foster motivation and creativity among employees, thereby strengthening their engagement in the process of generating and applying new ideas. Afsar and Umrani provide empirical support for this view, showing that transformational leadership significantly influences employees' IWB. [2]

Another important factor is perceived organizational support (POS), defined as employees' perception that the organization values their contributions and cares about their well-being. POS strengthens positive reciprocal feelings, which in turn encourage employees to perform behaviours that benefit the organization, including engaging in innovative behaviour. Numerous studies have shown that POS significantly influences IWB, either directly or through psychological variables such as thriving at work and work engagement. [3] [4]

Work engagement also plays a crucial role in understanding IWB. It represents a psychological state in which employees feel energized, enthusiastic, and motivated to give their best performance. Empirical research shows that employees with higher levels of work engagement are more open to idea development, more creative, and more committed to implementing innovations. [5] [6] At PPSDM Regional Yogyakarta, the average work engagement score of 3.04—categorized as moderate—indicates the need to enhance employees' psychological conditions to foster more consistent innovative behaviour.

Previous studies have revealed inconsistent findings regarding the relationships among transformational leadership, perceived organizational support, work engagement, and IWB. Some studies found significant positive relationships, while others reported differing results, particularly concerning the direct effects of TL on IWB and POS on IWB. These inconsistencies highlight the need for further investigation in the context of public organizations, especially within PPSDM Regional Yogyakarta, which is currently experiencing real challenges in strengthening its innovation culture.

These empirical conditions and theoretical discussions form the basis of this study, which aims to examine the influence of transformational leadership and perceived organizational support on innovative work behaviour, with a particular focus on the mediating role of work engagement. Strengthening work engagement is believed to be a key mechanism linking leadership and organizational support to employees' innovative behaviour. This study is expected to provide deeper insights into the factors that can enhance IWB among employees at PPSDM Regional Yogyakarta.

METHOD

This study employed a quantitative approach with an explanatory research design aimed at analyzing the causal relationships among transformational leadership, perceived organizational support, work engagement, and innovative work behaviour among civil servants at PPSDM Regional Yogyakarta. This approach was selected to examine both the direct and indirect effects among variables, as well as to test the theoretical model developed based on previous empirical findings. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire based on a Likert scale, covering all indicators of the research variables using instruments that have been validated in prior studies.

The study population consisted of all civil servants working at PPSDM Regional Yogyakarta. A total of 108 respondents were selected using a total sampling technique, considering the relatively small population size and the relevance of all members to the research model. The questionnaires were distributed online via a digital form and offline to employees present in their respective work units. The research instrument consisted of four main constructs—transformational leadership, perceived organizational support, work engagement, and innovative work behaviour—each adapted from previously validated measurement scales.

Data analysis was conducted using Partial Least Squares–Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) with the SmartPLS software. This technique was selected because it is suitable for examining complex relationships among constructs, accommodating relatively small sample sizes, and handling data that do not necessarily follow a normal distribution. The analysis process comprised two stages: (1) evaluation of the measurement model (outer model) to assess instrument validity and reliability, and (2) evaluation of the structural model (inner model) to test direct and indirect effects among variables, including the mediating role of work engagement. The findings were used to identify the variables that significantly contribute to enhancing employees’ innovative work behaviour.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Outer Model

Convergent Validity Test

The convergent validity test was conducted to ensure that each indicator within the research variables met the statistical feasibility requirements. Validity was assessed through the outer loading values of each indicator. Indicators are considered valid and appropriate for use if they have an outer loading value greater than 0.70 (Hair et al., 2017). A summary of the convergent validity results is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Loading Factor Values

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Loading Factor</i>	<i>Description</i>
Transformational Leadership	TL1	0.981	Valid
	TL2	0.989	Valid
	TL3	0.988	Valid
	TL4	0.983	Valid
	TL5	0.974	Valid
	TL6	0.966	Valid
	TL7	0.974	Valid
	TL8	0.960	Valid
Perceived Organizational Support	POS1	0.983	Valid
	POS2	0.983	Valid
	POS3	0.977	Valid
	POS4	0.979	Valid
	POS5	0.979	Valid
	POS6	0.978	Valid
Work Engagement	WE1	0.984	Valid
	WE2	0.986	Valid
	WE3	0.983	Valid
	WE4	0.984	Valid
	WE5	0.983	Valid
	WE6	0.982	Valid
Innovative Work Behaviour	IWB1	0.983	Valid
	IWB2	0.986	Valid
	IWB3	0.986	Valid
	IWB3	0.990	Valid
	IWB4	0.986	Valid
	IWB5	0.986	Valid

Source: Processed Data using SmartPLS version 3.2.9

The convergent validity results indicate that all indicators obtained loading factor values greater than 0.70, thus meeting the validity criteria. This demonstrates that each indicator contributes strongly to the construct it is intended to measure.

Figure 1. Structural Model

Discriminant Validity Test

In this study, discriminant validity was assessed using the Fornell–Larcker Criterion, a classical and widely used method for evaluating discriminant validity. [7] The results of the discriminant validity test are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Fornell–Larcker Criterion Results

Variable	Innovative Work Behaviour	Perceived Organizational Support	Transformational Leadership	Work Engagement
Innovative Work Behaviour	0.986			
Perceived Organizational Support	0.578	0.910		
Transformational Leadership	0.418	-0.057	0.977	
Work Engagement	0.756	0.444	0.465	0.984

Source: Data Processed using SmartPLS version 3.2.9

Based on Table 2, the square root of AVE for each variable is greater than its correlations with other variables, indicating that the discriminant validity criteria have been met.

Reliability Test

The reliability test was conducted to measure the internal consistency of each construct or variable in the questionnaire. An instrument is considered reliable when respondents’ answers to the items remain consistent over time. In this study, reliability was assessed to determine the internal consistency among indicators within each construct [8]. Composite reliability (CR) was used as the primary measure, as it is more appropriate in the Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) approach due to its lower sensitivity to the number of indicators and its ability to more accurately assess reliability. [7] A construct is considered reliable if its composite reliability value exceeds 0.6. The results of the reliability test are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Reliability Test Results

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Cronbach's Alpha</i>	<i>Composite Reliability</i>	<i>Description</i>
Transformational Leadership	0.993	0.994	Reliable
Perceived Organizational Support	0.992	0.993	Reliable
Work Engagement	0.993	0.994	Reliable
Innovative Work Behaviour	0.994	0.995	Reliable

Source: Data Processed using SmartPLS version 3.2.9

The results indicate that all variables have Cronbach’s alpha and composite reliability values above 0.6, as shown in Table 3. Thus, all constructs used in this study can be considered reliable.

Inner Model

R-Square

R-Square is used to measure the extent to which the variance of an endogenous variable (dependent variable) can be explained by the exogenous variables (independent and moderator variables) in the research model. Higher R-Square values indicate that the model possesses stronger explanatory power for the endogenous constructs. [7] The R-Square results of this study are presented in Table 4.

Table 4. R-Square

<i>Endogenous Variable</i>	<i>R Square</i>	<i>R Square Adjusted</i>
Work Engagement	0.439	0.428
Innovative Work Behaviour	0.675	0.665

Source: Data processed using SmartPLS version 3.2.9

Based on Table 4, the Adjusted R-Square value for Work Engagement is 0.428. This indicates that 42.8% of the variance in work engagement can be explained by the independent variables in the model, namely transformational leadership and perceived organizational support. The remaining 57.2% is explained by other factors outside the scope of this study, such as individual characteristics, work environment, or organizational culture.

Furthermore, the Adjusted R-Square value for Innovative Work Behaviour is 0.665. This means that 66.5% of the variance in innovative work behaviour is explained by the independent constructs examined in the model, including transformational leadership, perceived organizational support, and work engagement. The remaining 33.5% is influenced by other variables not included in the model.

Overall, the findings indicate that the research model demonstrates substantial predictive power, particularly for the Innovative Work Behaviour variable. The relatively high R-Square values suggest that the model effectively captures the relationships among constructs. These results also highlight the important mediating role of work engagement in strengthening the influence of transformational leadership and perceived organizational support on innovative work behaviour.

Q-Square

The Q-Square (Q²) test using the blindfolding technique is conducted to evaluate the predictive relevance of the structural model for the endogenous variables. A Q² value greater than zero indicates that the model has good predictive capability, whereas a Q² value ≤ 0 suggests that the model lacks predictive relevance [7].

Table 5. Q-Square Test Results

<i>Variable</i>	<i>SSO</i>	<i>SSE</i>	<i>Q² (= 1 - SSE/SSO)</i>
Work Engagement	648.000	375.623	0.420
Innovative Work Behaviour	648.000	224.213	0.651

Source: Data Processing using SmartPLS version 3.2.9

Based on Table 5, the Q² value for the Work Engagement variable is 0.420, while the Q² value for the Innovative Work Behaviour variable is 0.651. Since both values are greater than zero, it can be concluded that the model has good predictive relevance for all endogenous variables examined in this study.

The Q² value of 0.651 for innovative work behaviour indicates that the model is highly capable of predicting the variability of the observed data. This demonstrates that transformational leadership, perceived organizational support, and work engagement provide strong predictive contributions in explaining innovative work behaviour among civil servants at PPSDM Regional Yogyakarta.

Meanwhile, the Q² value of 0.420 for the work engagement variable also indicates that the model possesses adequate predictive capability, although not as strong as for innovative work behaviour. Overall, these findings confirm that the research model has sufficient predictive relevance, making it appropriate for explaining the causal relationships among variables in the context of this study.

Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis testing was carried out using the bootstrapping technique. This test aims to determine whether the relationships between variables in the structural model are statistically significant. The study employed a significance level of 5% ($\alpha = 0.05$), meaning that a hypothesis is accepted if the P-value is less than 0.05. The results of the hypothesis testing are presented in Table 6.

Table 6. Hypothesis Testing Results

Hypothesis Code	Hypothesis	Original Sample	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Value	Description
H ₁	Transformational Leadership → Innovative Work Behaviour	0.209	2.980	0.003	Accepted
H ₂	Perceived Organizational Support → Innovative Work Behaviour	0.370	4.782	0.000	Accepted
H ₃	Transformational Leadership → Work Engagement	0.492	7.085	0.000	Accepted
H ₄	Perceived Organizational Support → Work Engagement	0.472	6.775	0.000	Accepted
H ₅	Work Engagement → Innovative Work Behaviour	0.494	6.361	0.000	Accepted
H ₆	Perceived Organizational Support → Work Engagement → Innovative Work Behaviour	0.233	4.273	0.000	Accepted
H ₇	Transformational Leadership → Work Engagement → Innovative Work Behaviour	0.243	4.360	0.000	Accepted

Source: Data Processing using SmartPLS version 3.2.9

The results of the hypothesis testing in Table 6 indicate that:

Hypothesis H1 is accepted, with a P-value of $0.003 < 0.05$ and a T-statistic of 2.980. This shows that transformational leadership has a positive and significant effect on innovative work behaviour. This means that the higher the level of transformational leadership perceived by employees, the higher the level of innovative work behaviour demonstrated by Civil Servants at the Human Resources Development Center (PPSDM) Regional Yogyakarta.

Hypothesis H2 is accepted, with a P-value of $0.000 < 0.05$ and a T-statistic of 4.782. This indicates that perceived organizational support has a positive and significant effect on innovative work behaviour. In other words, the greater the organizational support perceived by employees, the stronger their encouragement to engage in innovative behaviour at work.

Hypothesis H3 is accepted, with a P-value of $0.000 < 0.05$ and a T-statistic of 7.085. This finding shows that transformational leadership has a positive and significant effect on work engagement. This means that the more effective the transformational leadership style implemented by leaders, the higher the employees' work engagement toward their tasks and responsibilities.

Hypothesis H4 is accepted, with a P-value of $0.000 < 0.05$ and a T-statistic of 6.775. This result indicates that perceived organizational support has a positive and significant effect on work engagement. Thus, strong organizational support enhances employees' enthusiasm, dedication, and involvement in carrying out their duties.

Hypothesis H5 is accepted, with a P-value of $0.000 < 0.05$ and a T-statistic of 6.361. This means that work engagement has a positive and significant effect on innovative work behaviour. In other words, the higher the employee's engagement at work, the greater their tendency to generate and apply new ideas in their job context.

Hypothesis H6 is accepted, with a P-value of $0.000 < 0.05$ and a T-statistic of 4.273. This result shows that work engagement mediates the effect of perceived organizational support on innovative work behaviour. This means that organizational support perceived by employees increases their work engagement, which in turn encourages innovative work behaviour.

Hypothesis H7 is accepted, with a P-value of $0.000 < 0.05$ and a T-statistic of 4.360. This finding demonstrates that work engagement mediates the effect of transformational leadership on innovative work behaviour. In other words, strong transformational leadership enhances employees' work engagement, which subsequently strengthens their tendency to behave innovatively in carrying out their tasks.

DISCUSSION

The Influence of Transformational Leadership on Innovative Work Behaviour

The analysis shows that transformational leadership has a positive and significant effect on innovative work behaviour among civil servants at PPSDM Regional Yogyakarta. This finding indicates that the greater the implementation of transformational leadership by leaders, the more likely employees are to demonstrate innovative work behaviours. Transformational leadership is considered effective because it not only emphasizes the leader's creativity but also encourages employees to actively participate in developing new ideas through empowerment and enhanced self-confidence. [9] Bass and Avolio further explain that transformational leadership is a process in which leaders serve as ideal role models, provide intellectual stimulation, inspiration, and support that guide employees toward achieving the organization's shared vision and goals. [10] Similarly, Setiawan and Muhith emphasize that this leadership style has the capacity to transform organizations in responding to change. [11]

However, the questionnaire results show that respondents' perceptions of transformational leadership are still in the moderate category, with an average mean score of 3.01. This indicates that transformational leadership practices at PPSDM Regional Yogyakarta are not yet optimal. Specifically, the item with the lowest mean score (2.99) is "The leader provides guidance according to my potential." This suggests that some employees feel they have not received mentorship aligned with their individual potential. In other words, although leaders have served as role models and are able to inspire employees (with mean scores of 3.02–3.05), the aspect of personalized guidance still needs improvement.

This condition illustrates that the positive influence of transformational leadership on innovative work behaviour is driven more by inspirational and role-modeling aspects, rather than targeted mentoring for potential development. Yet, guidance that aligns with employees' potential is crucial in creating a work environment conducive to generating ideas and innovation. This aligns with findings by Afsar and Umrani and Saif et al. (2024), who highlight that transformational leadership effectively encourages innovative work behaviour when leaders can tailor their approaches to the needs and characteristics of their subordinates.[2][12] Thus, although the statistical results show a positive and significant influence, empirical conditions among employees at PPSDM Regional Yogyakarta indicate that improving the quality of mentoring and individual potential development is still necessary. Efforts such as coaching, mentoring, or competency-based assessments can strengthen the personal relationship between leaders and employees, ultimately enhancing innovative work behaviour within the organization.

The Influence of Perceived Organizational Support on Innovative Work Behaviour

The analysis shows that perceived organizational support (POS) has a positive and significant effect on innovative work behaviour among civil servants at PPSDM Regional Yogyakarta. This means that the higher the organizational support perceived by employees, the more likely they are to exhibit innovative work behaviours.

According to organizational support theory introduced by Eisenberger et al., employees form a general perception of the extent to which the organization values their contributions and cares about their well-being. This perception is referred to as perceived organizational support.[13] There are three main factors that enhance POS: organizational justice, supervisor support, and rewards along with good working conditions. These factors directly influence employees' sense of security, loyalty, and involvement in their work. [14]

Based on the questionnaire results, respondents' perceptions of POS at PPSDM Regional Yogyakarta fall into the moderate category, with an average mean score of 2.96. This indicates that although the organization has provided certain forms of support, some employees do not fully perceive adequate appreciation or concern from the organization. The items with the lowest mean scores are: "Organizational policies are applied consistently to all employees" (mean 2.94) and "I feel appreciated for the contributions I make" (mean 2.94). These conditions suggest the presence of inconsistent policy implementation and a lack of recognition, which can reduce employees' sense of fairness and personal acknowledgment in the workplace.

This finding is important because perceptions of fairness and recognition are foundational to developing a sense of organizational support. When employees feel that policies are not applied fairly or that appreciation is not proportional, their motivation to engage in innovative behaviour may decline. In fact, strong organizational support can foster psychological safety, strengthen emotional commitment, and encourage the emergence of new ideas from employees.

This is in line with research by Ergun et al., which shows that organizational support significantly contributes to innovative work behaviour by strengthening confidence, motivation, and employee engagement in innovation. [15] Similarly, studies by Nana et al., confirm that POS encourages creativity through feelings of appreciation and recognition from the organization. [16] Therefore, although statistical tests show a positive and significant effect, empirical findings indicate that employees' perceptions of organizational support are still moderate. PPSDM Regional Yogyakarta should reinforce organizational justice and transparent reward systems so that employees feel increasingly valued and supported. Such efforts not only enhance job satisfaction but also have the potential to strengthen innovative work behaviour in a sustainable manner.

The Influence of Transformational Leadership on Work Engagement

The analysis shows that transformational leadership has a positive and significant effect on work engagement among civil servants at PPSDM Regional Yogyakarta. This finding indicates that the higher the quality of transformational leadership implemented by leaders, the higher the employees' work engagement. Transformational leaders focus not only on achieving organizational goals but also on developing employees through motivation, support, and empowerment. [9] Bass and Avolio emphasize that transformational leadership fosters emotional connections with employees through inspiration, intellectual stimulation, and individualized consideration, ultimately fostering a sense of belonging and engagement at work. [10]

This result is consistent with the findings of Ariesta et al., who show that transformational leadership enhances work engagement through the creation of a clear and inspiring vision. [5] Widasti and Mursid also demonstrate that positive perceptions of transformational leadership can strengthen work engagement because employees feel valued and supported in their contributions. In other words, transformational leadership acts as a source of emotional energy that makes employees more enthusiastic, focused, and committed to their work [17].

However, based on the questionnaire results, respondents' perceptions of transformational leadership and work engagement both fall within the moderate category (mean scores 3.01 and 3.04 respectively). This suggests that although the influence is statistically significant, the implementation of transformational leadership values in practice has not yet been maximized in increasing employees' engagement.

The item with the lowest mean score for transformational leadership is "The leader provides guidance according to my potential" (mean 2.99), indicating limited individualized consideration. This aligns with relatively low mean scores for work engagement items such as "I feel fully focused when performing tasks" and "I feel energized when carrying out my work" (mean 3.02). These data logically connect: when leaders do not fully provide personalized support based on individual potential, employees' energy, focus, and emotional engagement also remain suboptimal.

This is consistent with Contreras, who notes that the influence of transformational leadership on work engagement can vary depending on organizational context, work culture, and reward systems. In the context of PPSDM Regional Yogyakarta, transformational leadership seems to have laid a strong foundation of inspiration and motivation, but individualized mentoring and empowerment remain limited. [18]

Thus, although statistical results show a positive and significant influence, the practical implementation still remains moderate. The organization therefore needs to strengthen the dimension of individualized consideration through more structured coaching and mentoring. This approach is expected to enhance employees' emotional engagement, work enthusiasm, and sense of belonging to the organization.

The Influence of Perceived Organizational Support on Work Engagement

The analysis shows that perceived organizational support has a positive and significant effect on work engagement among civil servants at PPSDM Regional Yogyakarta. This means that the higher the organizational support perceived by employees, the greater their level of engagement in their work. Perceived organizational support reflects employees' perceptions of the extent to which the organization values their contributions and cares about their well-being (Eisenberger et al., 2020). Based on social exchange theory, when employees perceive strong organizational support, they tend to reciprocate by increasing their dedication, energy, and focus at work as a positive return to the organization. [14]

The questionnaire results show that respondents' perceptions of organizational support fall in the moderate category, with an average mean score of 2.96. The lowest-scoring items include "Organizational policies are applied consistently to all employees" (mean 2.94) and "I feel appreciated for the contributions I make" (mean 2.94). This indicates that some employees feel that the implementation of policies and recognition is not yet fully consistent or equitable in the workplace. Such perceptions may influence the extent to which employees feel valued by the organization, ultimately affecting their level of work engagement.

Similarly, the work engagement questionnaire results also fall in the moderate category (mean 3.04), with relatively low scores for items such as "I feel full of energy when performing my job" (mean 3.02) and "I feel completely focused when carrying out tasks" (mean 3.02). This pattern shows an empirical relationship: when employees perceive organizational support as limited, their energy, dedication, and work focus also tend to be less optimal.

These findings are consistent with Ergun et al., who state that organizational support plays a crucial role in increasing employees' enthusiasm, dedication, and work engagement. [15] Aldabbas et al., also found that POS enhances intrinsic motivation, encouraging employees to work wholeheartedly. Strong organizational support manifested through fairness, supervisory care, and transparent reward systems contributes to psychological safety and strengthens employees' affective commitment to their work. [19]

Thus, although statistically POS has a positive and significant effect on work engagement, the empirical results indicate that the level of organizational support at PPSDM Regional Yogyakarta still needs improvement. Efforts to enhance fairness in policy implementation, recognition of employee contributions, and open communication between leaders and staff can strengthen the sense of organizational support. If these steps are optimized, employee work engagement has the potential to rise from moderate to high, ultimately contributing positively to organizational performance and innovation.

The Influence of Work Engagement on Innovative Work Behaviour

The analysis shows that work engagement has a positive and significant effect on innovative work behaviour among civil servants at PPSDM Regional Yogyakarta. Work engagement reflects employees' emotional and psychological attachment to their job, characterized by enthusiasm, dedication, and full concentration in carrying out tasks. Employees with high levels of work engagement not only strive to deliver their best performance but are also motivated to propose creative and innovative ideas. When engagement is high, individuals internalize organizational goals as personal goals, thereby developing a commitment to contribute through innovative work behaviour. [15]

Previous studies support the positive influence of work engagement on innovative work behaviour (IWB). Hidayat et al. (2021), Ariesta et al. (2024), and Alateeg & Alhammadi (2024) found that work engagement strengthens employee creativity, which in turn drives innovation. Widasti & Mursid add that employees with high engagement strive to produce new and useful ideas for their organization. Thus, work engagement becomes a significant driver in fostering an innovation-oriented culture. [17]

Based on the questionnaire results, the average respondent score for work engagement is 3.04, classified as moderate. This indicates that while most employees have fairly good engagement, it is not yet fully optimal. In other words, although employees possess energy and enthusiasm for their work, there remains room to further enhance their emotional and psychological attachment.

Meanwhile, the innovative work behaviour variable shows an average score of 3.09, also in the moderate category. This indicates that employees display moderate levels of innovative behaviour—such as proposing new ideas, seeking more effective work methods, and assisting in implementing new ideas—though the intensity is not yet high. This condition aligns with the statistical results showing a positive and significant relationship between work engagement and innovative work behaviour.

Therefore, this study reinforces the view that work engagement serves as a catalyst for innovative behaviour. However, since both work engagement and innovative work behaviour are still in the moderate category, this indicates that although the influence is significant, its practical implementation still needs strengthening. Efforts to enhance motivation, organizational support, and a more stimulating work environment are needed to encourage employees to be more energetic, committed, and driven toward innovation.

The Mediating Role of Work Engagement in the Influence of Transformational Leadership on Innovative Work Behaviour

The analysis indicates that work engagement mediates the effect of transformational leadership on innovative work behaviour among civil servants at PPSDM Regional Yogyakarta. Based on questionnaire results, the transformational leadership variable has an average score of 3.01 (moderate category). This indicates that most employees perceive their leaders as showing transformational characteristics at a moderate level such as being role models, providing work enthusiasm, conveying a clear vision, and supporting personal development but not yet fully optimal in consistently providing intellectual stimulation and individualized consideration.

This condition aligns with the moderate average score of work engagement (3.04), indicating that employee engagement is also at a moderate level. In other words, although employees show energy and dedication in their work, the intensity of their engagement could still be improved.

Theoretically, Bass and Avolio explain that transformational leaders enhance work engagement by fostering trust, inspiration, and supportive relationships with employees. Leaders who demonstrate individualized consideration and intellectual stimulation create a work environment that nurtures enthusiasm and commitment. [10] In this study, work engagement acts as the psychological mechanism that bridges the influence of transformational leadership on innovative work behaviour.

These findings are in line with Widasti & Mursid, who found that work engagement is a significant mediating variable between transformational leadership and innovative behaviour. [17] Similarly, Ariesta et al., emphasize that work engagement functions as a key pathway through which transformational leaders encourage innovation. When leaders provide inspiration and motivation, employees become more emotionally and psychologically engaged, which in turn increases their willingness to propose, develop, and implement new ideas in the workplace. [5]

However, since both transformational leadership and work engagement remain in the moderate category, the mediating effect is not yet fully optimal. PPSDM Regional Yogyakarta needs to strengthen transformational leadership practices, particularly in the areas of individualized consideration and intellectual stimulation, to increase employee engagement so that their innovative potential can be more fully realized.

The Mediating Role of Work Engagement in the Influence of Perceived Organizational Support on Innovative Work Behaviour

The results indicate that work engagement mediates the effect of perceived organizational support on innovative work behaviour among civil servants at PPSDM Regional Yogyakarta. The average score of POS is 2.96 (moderate category), indicating that while employees perceive a fair level of organizational support, it is not yet optimal. Several aspects—such as fairness, recognition of contributions, and consistency in policy implementation—are still viewed as insufficiently strong. This condition influences work engagement, which is also in the moderate category (mean 3.04). This means that although employees demonstrate energy, enthusiasm, and dedication in their work, their level of emotional and psychological involvement is not yet maximized. The organizational support they perceive has not fully generated stronger intrinsic motivation or affective commitment.

Theoretically, Eisenberger et al., explain that perceived organizational support reflects the extent to which employees believe their organization values their contributions and cares about their well-being. When POS is high, employees reciprocate with positive attitudes such as greater work engagement and innovative behaviour. [13] Supportive organizational environments create psychological safety, strengthen reciprocal relationships, and foster the energy and enthusiasm needed for innovation.

These findings are consistent with studies by Ranihusna et al., Hidayat et al., and Dogru, which show that POS significantly influences innovative work behaviour through work engagement. Strong organizational support enhances intrinsic motivation and emotional involvement, prompting employees to contribute more through generating and implementing new ideas at work. Thus, work engagement serves as the psychological bridge explaining how organizational support fosters innovative behaviour. [20][21][22]

However, given that POS remains at a moderate level, these findings indicate that organizational support at PPSDM Regional Yogyakarta still needs improvement. Efforts should focus on policy transparency, recognizing employee contributions, and demonstrating genuine care for employee well-being. Strengthening these dimensions will increase employees' work engagement, which in turn will positively contribute to sustainable increases in innovative work behaviour.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The findings of this study indicate that transformational leadership and perceived organizational support have a positive and significant effect on innovative work behaviour, both directly and through the mediating role of work engagement among civil servants at PPSDM Regional Yogyakarta. Transformational leadership is proven to enhance employees' enthusiasm, dedication, and emotional attachment, while organizational support encourages creativity, initiative, and employees' contributions in generating new ideas. Work engagement functions as an important psychological mechanism that strengthens the relationship between leadership, organizational support, and innovative work behaviour, making it a key factor in transforming a supportive work environment into enhanced innovation capacity within the public sector.

The study further highlights that perceived organizational support is the strongest predictor of innovative work behaviour. Thus, employees' perceptions of fairness, appreciation, and consistency in policy implementation become critical aspects in fostering innovation in the workplace. The lowest-scoring POS indicators—namely, consistency in policy implementation and feeling appreciated for contributions—indicate the need to strengthen organizational support at PPSDM Regional Yogyakarta. This can be achieved through improving transparency and uniformity in policy implementation, establishing open communication between leaders and employees, and applying sustainable appreciation mechanisms such as performance-based rewards, public recognition of employee achievements, or opportunities for competence development. Strengthening these aspects is essential to creating a fair and supportive work climate that encourages employees to be more engaged, contribute creatively, and enhance their innovative work behaviour.

REFERENCES

1. Mumford MD, Scott GM, Gaddis B, Strange JM. Leading creative people: Orchestrating expertise and relationships. *The Leadership Quarterly*. 2000;11(4):705–750. doi:10.1016/S1048-9843(00)00078-8.
2. Afsar B, Umrani WA. Transformational leadership and innovative work behaviour. *European Journal of Innovation Management*. 2020;23(3):402–428. doi:10.1108/EJIM-12-2018-0277.
3. Jamal M, Khan A, Noor H. Perceived organizational support and innovative work behaviour: Testing direct and indirect effects. *Asian Journal of Business and Management*. 2023;11(3):55–66.
4. Hidayat M, Nugroho A, Prasetyo W. Public sector innovation in the era of disruption. *Jurnal Administrasi Publik*. 2023;19(2):145–160.
5. Ariesta D, Nugroho H, Sari M. Work engagement as a mediator between organizational support and innovative work behaviour. *Journal of Behavioural Science*. 2024;15(2):221–235. doi:10.14456/jbs.2024.15.
6. Ergun S, Yildiz B, Ozturk M. The impact of perceived organizational support on innovative work behaviour: The mediating role of work engagement. *Journal of Organizational Change Management*. 2025;38(1):21–39. doi:10.1108/JOCM-05-2023-0134.
7. Hair JF, Hult GTM, Ringle C, Sarstedt M. *A primer on partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM)*. 2nd ed. Sage Publications; 2019.
8. Ghozali I. *Aplikasi analisis multivariate dengan program IBM SPSS 25*. Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro; 2018.
9. Robbins SP, Judge TA. *Organizational behaviour*. 17th ed. Pearson Education; 2017.
10. Bass BM, Avolio BJ. Transformational leadership and organizational culture. *Public Administration Quarterly*. 1993;17(1):112–121.

11. Setiawan E, Muhith A. *Transformational leadership dalam organisasi publik*. Airlangga University Press; 2013.
12. Saif M, Ali H, Ahmed K. Transformational leadership and innovative work behaviour: Empirical evidence from public sector employees. *Journal of Leadership Studies*. 2024;18(1):55–70.
13. Eisenberger R, Malone GP, Presson WD. Optimizing perceived organizational support to enhance employee engagement. *Society for Human Resource Management*. 2020;19(1):133–151.
14. Rosyiana D. *Perilaku kerja inovatif dalam organisasi publik*. Prenadamedia Group; 2019.
15. Nana D, Susanto A, Wibowo S. Perceived organizational support and employee innovation: The mediating role of job satisfaction. *International Journal of Innovation Studies*. 2024;8(2):99–110.
16. Widasti R, Mursid S. The mediating role of work engagement in the relationship between transformational leadership and innovative work behaviour. *International Journal of Social Management*. 2022;7(2):122–135.
17. Contreras F, Baykal E, Abid G. E-leadership and teleworking in times of COVID-19 and beyond: What we know and where do we go. *Frontiers in Psychology*. 2020;11:590271. doi:10.3389/fpsyg.2020.590271.
18. Aldabbas H, Pinnington A, Lahrech A. The influence of perceived organizational support on innovative work behaviour: The mediation role of work engagement. *International Journal of Organizational Analysis*. 2021;29(2):342–358. doi:10.1108/IJOA-05-2019-1747.
19. Ranihusna D, Cahyono E, Sari N. Work engagement as a mediator in the relationship between perceived organizational support and innovative work behaviour. *Jurnal Manajemen dan Kewirausahaan*. 2021;23(2):133–144.
20. Dogru M. The mediating role of work engagement on the relationship between organizational support and innovative work behaviour. *Journal of Human Resources*. 2018;36(4):55–72.

Cite this Article: Sulistyaningrum, D.A., Subyantoro, A., Nilmawati (2025). *The Influence of Transformational Leadership and Perceived Organizational Support on Innovative Work Behaviour Mediated by Work Engagement among Civil Servants at PPSDM Regional Yogyakarta*. *International Journal of Current Science Research and Review*, 8(11), pp. 5796-5807. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.47191/ijcsrr/V8-i11-36>